

Analysis of Influence of Training, Emotional Intelligence, and Organizational Culture to Employees performance at STTP Medan, North Sumatra, Indonesia

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study is to examine the effect of training, emotional intelligence, and organizational culture on employee performance simultaneously or partially. The purpose of the research is to obtain effective policy formulation as an improvement of employee performance. All employees of higher education are 46 people as research respondents. This type of research is quantitative descriptive. Data collection was conducted by distributing questionnaires directly to employees and with secondary data. Data analysis model using a multiple linear regression model. The results indicated that training, emotional intelligence, and organizational culture significantly affected the performance of employees simultaneously and partially. The emotional intelligence variables become the most influential variables on employee performance, followed by organizational training and culture variables. We suggested as follow (1) Providing training to employees according to the needs of employees. (2) Entering spiritual activities once a month to each employee's house on a rotation which is followed by all members of the family of the employee (3) Paste the organization culture slogan infrequently visited places and easily seen. (4) Conducting the control of the attendance of employees in the office.

Keywords: Training, Emotional Intelligence, Organization Culture, Human Resources and Employees Performance

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Introduction

STPP Medan is an institution of higher education organized by the Ministry of Agriculture. The implementation of STPP under the Organization for Training and Human Resources Development Agriculture. The goal of STPP Medan is to prepare and fulfill the needs of experts in agribusiness agriculture extension and counseling, with technical and managerial skills capable of independently managing and developing an agribusiness system productively, effectively and efficiently to support agricultural development (STPP Medan, 2017). Officer as Human Resources (HR) found in the organization. Managing Human resources well is the key to organizational success to achieve the goals set. One of the ways to manage Human Resources is to provide the training needed by the tasks undertaken by the Human Resources. Nasution (2015) believes that the company's education and training to employees is an investment company that aims to develop human capital that will ultimately improve the company's performance. Another factor affecting employee performance is emotional intelligence. Goleman (2003) points out that the most significant ability that affects one's success in work is empathy, self-discipline, and an initiative known as emotional intelligence. Things that affect success. Research conducted by Hariyati (2012) shows that the organizational culture has a significant effect on performance. Rivai (2012) believes organizational culture is a framework that guarantees daily behavior and makes decisions for employees and directs actions to achieve organizational goals. Organizations are expected to run under the stated goals. Goal achievement will be achieved with good organization performance. A good performance team will form good organizational performance. This case is in line with Prawirosentono's (1999) opinion, which states that performance is the result of work that can be achieved by a person or group of people within an organization by their respective authorities and responsibilities. In order to reach the goals of the organization concerned legally, do not breaking the law and by morals and ethics. Achieving an organization's goals is one of the most dependent on the poor performance of employees, so organizations should be able to pay attention to employees, directing, and motivating to improve employee performance. Good-performing employees will be able to run their jobs by the tasks they are charged, understand their job relevance with others, understand the organization's targets, and overcome the difficulties faced in carrying out their duties. Based on interviews and problem identification, the author formulated some hypotheses in this study as follows:

H1: Training has a significant effect on the performance of STPP Medan.

H2: Emotional Intelligence has a significant effect on the performance of STPP Medan.

H3: Organizational Culture has a significant effect on the performance of STPP Medan

H4: Training, Emotional Intelligence, and Organizational Culture have significant effect on the performance of STPP Medan

Literature Review Performance

Performance according to Robbins and Judge (2013) is behaviors that include: (1) Work results. Performing the duties and responsibilities that contribute to the production of goods or services or administrative tasks. This case includes most of the tasks in general work description. (2) Concern. Actions that contribute to the organizational psychological environment, such as helping others when needed, supporting organizational goals, treating colleagues with respect, making suggestive builds, and saying positive things about the workplace. (3) Contra productivity. Actions that are actively damaging the organization. This behavior includes stealing, damaging the property of the company, behaving aggressively

against colleagues, and attendance at the office does not fit the working hours. Something that can provide instructions or information that will affect performance. Nasution (2015) that the company's education and training to employees is an investment company that aims to develop human capital that will ultimately improve the company's performance. In Goleman's (2003) research in Harseno (2014) shows that the most significant ability that affects one's success in work is empathy, self-discipline, and an initiative known as emotional intelligence. Emotional intelligence is a crucial factor in the satisfaction and performance of employees. Employee satisfaction has an active role in mediate emotional intelligence on employee performance (Wirawan, 2017). Organizational culture elements into an indicator as Rahadi (2010) reveals the success of a performance management implementation is heavily influenced by the soft side factor that is how all layers within the company change the old paradigm, from 8-5 culture. That means entering 8 am back home at 5 pm, to culture have given a value added to the company today? Perhaps this question is very relevant if we ask each other ourselves before we implement performance management. Furthermore, Rivai and Basri (2004) in Rahadi (2010) stated that performance assessments were also useful for the company. Improving all units of the units in the enterprise because communication becomes more effective in corporate purposes and corporate values. Furthermore, the corporate culture became established.

Training

Poniman and Hadiyat (2015) suggest that training is a process for providing knowledge, skills, and abilities specific to tasks and work. According to Regulation of the Minister of Agriculture No. 120 (2014), training is a teaching-learning activity to improve the competence of a specific skill or skill level according to the level and qualifications of the work. A broader sense is given by Watung at al (2016) that training and development is a process of learning and business undertaken by companies/organizations to improve their employees' work skills. Development is more aimed at improving managerial skills, while training is more geared towards improving the technical skills to obtain: 1) Improving work skills, 2) Understanding the work properly, 3) Working in the right way. Rosidah (2009) points out that necessary training is done because it is the organizational way to guard and maintain, to improve the skills of employees, then to improve their productivity. In training created an environment where employees can learn attitudes and skills, and specific behaviors associated with employees, and are given instructions to develop their skills that can be used directly in order to improve the performance of employees in their occupation. Training is conducted for new employees in order to carry out new duties charged and for longtime employees to improve the quality of their current and future duties. It is explained that training is part of education that involves the learning process to acquire and improve skills beyond the appropriate educational system in a relatively short period and with a more practical method of practice than theory (Ardana et al., 2012).

Emotional Intelligence

Jaya et al. (2012) convey the emotional intelligence of an employee is a determining factor in performance success, because in an emotional intelligence an employee can control all his ego and his desire and be able to understand others or his colleagues to create a dynamic working group atmosphere. Emotional Intelligence is one's ability to (1) feel emotions in themselves and others, (2) understand the meaning of this emotion, and (3) control one's emotions. People who know their own emotions and standards read emotional cues, for example, knowing why they are angry and how to express themselves without breaking the norms

most likely to be effective (Robbins and Judge, 2013). The sign of one's emotional intelligence according to Tridhonanto (2009) is as follows: (1) Personal skills, namely the ability to manage oneself. (2) Skills in socializing, that is, the ability to deal with a relationship. (3) Social skills, which are the ability to motivate the responses that others want. Something can provide, as Goleman (2009) discloses emotional intelligence or clues. Emotional can be a guide for individuals to achieve success, namely (1): self-esteem, the ability of an individual to function to monitor feelings over time, to look at feelings that emerge. The inability to perceive the real feelings signifies that people are in emotional power. (2) Self-regulation, the ability to comfort themselves, to eliminate anxiety, depression or intimidation and consequences arising from the failure of basic emotional skills. Someone who has low ability in managing emotions will continue to take shelter against moodiness while those with high levels of emotional management will be able to rise faster than their depression. The ability to manage emotions includes self-control and self-reliance ability. (3) Motivation, the ability to regulate emotions into tools to achieve goals and self-control. Someone who has this skill tends to be more productive and effective in whatever effort he or she does. This ability is based on the ability to control emotions that restrain themselves to satisfaction and control the urge. (4). Reinforce the emotions of others (empathy) that is the ability that relies on consciousness. This ability is a necessary skill in socializing. Empathy is better able to capture hidden social signals that imply what other people need or want. (5). Social skills, which are the skills of managing others' emotions, maintaining relationships with others through social skills, leadership, and personal relationships.

Organizational Culture

According to Robbins and Judge (2013), organizational culture is a shared sense system owned by members that differentiate organizations from other organizations. Anshari et al. (2014) suggest organizational cultural values that make bureaucratic neutral, proportional and professional should be developed into an organizational culture that will help the organizations of the agencies become effective in carrying out their primary duties and functions. Although this problem is indeed a complicated task, it is imperative to note that the government wants to succeed in realizing the welfare of society. Organizational culture can be described as values, norms and artifacts received by organizational members as organizational climate it will influence and influence organizational strategy, organizational structure, and systems (Amstrong 1994, in Banendroa et al., 2016). Robbins and Judge (2013) argue that there are seven main organizational cultural characteristics, namely: (1) Innovation and risk-taking. Levels where employees are encouraged to become innovative and risky. (2). Attention to detail. The level at which the employee is expected to demonstrate precision, analysis, and attention to detail. (3). Result orientation. The level at which the management focuses on the outcome of the techniques and processes used to achieve it. (4) An orientation of persons. To what extent management decisions consider the impact of outcomes on people within the organization. (5). Team orientation. The level in which work activity is organized around the team rather than the individual. (6) Aggressiveness. Levels in which people are aggressive and competitive rather than relaxed. (7). Stability. The extent to which organizational activity emphasizes retaining its original condition in contrast to growth.

Research Methods

This type of research is based on descriptive quantitative methods with associative approaches. According to Sugiyono (2014), associative research is a study that aims to

determine the relationship between two or more variables, to find the role, and the effect, the causal relationship, that is between independent variables and dependent variables. The populations in this study are all employees of STPP, Medan which amounted to 46 respondents. Method of data analysis in this research used multiple linear regression model. In the process of data processing, the writer uses the data processing software of Statistical software Product and Service Solution (SPSS).

Research & Discussion

Results

Validity Test

With a total sample of 46 respondents, the correlation analysis was conducted between the questionnaire score and the validity value (r-critical). For the r product moment (r-critical), at 46 samples, with a significant level of 5% is 0.361, if the r-count-value is higher or equal to 0.361, then it can be stated that the instrument is valid. Thus the whole question in the questionnaires is declared valid (Sinulingga, 2014). The following table of validity test results of the research instrument is as follows:

Table 1: Validity Test Results

Variables	Item	r-count-value	r-critical value	Description
Training (X1)	X1-1	0,656	0,361	Valid
	X1-2	0,768	0,361	Valid
	X1-3	0,531	0,361	Valid
	X1-4	0,793	0,361	Valid
Emotional Intelligence (X2)	X2-1	0,444	0,361	Valid
	X2-2	0,541	0,361	Valid
	X2-3	0,497	0,361	Valid
	X2-4	0,586	0,361	Valid
	X2-5	0,486	0,361	Valid
Organizational Culture (X3)	X3-1	0,377	0,361	Valid
	X3-2	0,464	0,361	Valid
	X3-3	0,558	0,361	Valid
Performance (Y)	Y1-1	0,574	0,361	Valid
	Y1-2	0,411	0,361	Valid
	Y1-3	0,497	0,361	Valid
	Y1-4	0,565	0,361	Valid

Reliability Test

In this study, the Cronbach alpha coefficient calculated as the average correlation between the items in the set. If the alpha Cronbach coefficient-value is closer to value one then the stronger internal consistency reliability (Sinulingga 2017).

Table 2: Reliability Test Results

Variables	Alpha Cronbach's Value	Description
Training (X1)	0,847	Reliable
Emotional Intelligence (X2)	0,741	Reliable
Organizational Culture (X3)	0,636	Reliable
Performance (Y)	0,716	Reliable

Hypothesis Test

Simultaneous Test Results (F-Test)

Table 3. Simultaneous Test Results

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	90.039	3	30.013	14.121	.000 ^b
Residual	89.265	42	2.125		
Total	179.304	45			

a. Dependent Variable: Performance

Predictors: (Constant), Organizational_Cultural, Emotional_Intelligence, Training

At table 3 it can be calculated F-count at 14,121 shows the value of F-count (14,121) > from F-table (2,83) and level of significance test F equal to 0,000 (0,000 < 0,05) then H_0 is rejected and H_1 accepted. It means there is a significant influence of training (X1), emotional intelligence (X2), and organizational culture (X3) on performance (Y) simultaneously. From the above test results, this hypothesis is accepted.

Partial Test (T-test)

Table 4 : Partial Test Results

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.090	2.324		.899	.374
	Training	.278	.083	.382	3.348	.002
	Emotional_Intelligence	.297	.087	.379	3.415	.001
	Organizational_Cultural	.395	.133	.334	2.978	.005

Dependent Variable: Performance

Based on the data in Table 4 can be explained as follows: The partial t-value of the Training variable (X1) is obtained as the result of the t-count value is 3,348, and the t-table value is 2,015 so the t-count > t-table (3,348 > 2,015) and the sig value < 05 (0,002 < 0,05). It can be concluded that Training has a very significant effect on the performance of officer STPP, Medan, 3,348. The value of t partially from the Emotional Intelligence variable (X2) is obtained the result is the t-count value is 3,415, and the t-table value is 1.656, the t-count > t-table (3,415 > 2,015) and sig < 0,05 (0,001 < 0,05), it can be concluded that the partial Emotional Intelligence has a significant effect on the performance of officer STPP, Medan 3,415. The value of t partially from Organizational Culture variable (X3) is obtained by the result of the tcount-value of Organizational Culture is 2,978 and the value of t-table is 2,015 so the t-count > t-table (2,978 > 2,015) 0,05 (0,005 < 0,05). It can be concluded that Organizational Culture by partially significant influence to performance of officer STPP, Medan 2,978. The value of t partially from the Training variable (X1) is obtained as a result of the t-count value of the Emotional Intelligence variable is 3,415 and the t-table value is 2,015, the t-count > t-table (3,415 > 2,015) and the sig value < 0,05 (0,001 < 0,05). It can be concluded

that Emotional Intelligence by partial is dominant variable that has significant effect to Performance of Officer STPP is 3,415

Discussion

Influence of Training (X1) on Employee Performance (Y)

The result of the research shows that there is a positive influence between the training to the performance of the employee in STPP, Medan. Providing training to employees is indispensable. Training is being conducted for new employees in order to carry out new duties charged and for longtime employees to improve the quality of their current and future duties. In training created an environment where employees can improve their knowledge, skills, and specific attitudes relating to employees. In training, the employees are given instructions to develop their skills that can be used directly in order to improve the performance of employees in the occupation. Elnaga and Imran (2013) stated that the primary purpose of each training session is to add value to employee performance, so all types of business design their training and development programs for their employees as a continuous activity. Elnaga further stated that the purpose of training is what will be achieved by employees after undergoing training programs. Some organizations plan and implement training programs for their employees without identifying goals and objectives and without knowing what the knowledge, skills, and capabilities of employees will be learned at the end of the training program and whether they will be able to achieve performance targets at work. Therefore, the company must design a training program with clear goals and objectives while keeping in mind the special needs of individuals and organizations. The results of the study were conducted by Mumu et al. (2015) that training has a partial effect on PT. Hasjrat Multifinance Manado, and is the most influential variable. The same is also mentioned by Mamahit (2013) that training has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. This case means that with the training the agency can produce human resources that have optimal performance. With training activities, employees have the opportunity to absorb new knowledge or values, so with that new knowledge, the employees can improve their profession in carrying out their assigned tasks. The organization should consider all aspects of the research results. Organizations should choose the most appropriate training intervention — training that helps the organization to solve all the problems and increase the level of employee motivation to participate and meet the expectations of the organization by demonstrating the desired performance.

Emotional Intelligence (X2) Influence on Employee Performance

The positive effect of emotional intelligence on the performance of employees of STPP, Medan was generated in this study. The things that emerge in the employee's emotional intelligence will affect the success of the work. This case should be owned by all employees. Starting from top management level, middle, lower level, even level of execution. With the emotional intelligence it is revealed that one can recognize the feelings of oneself, be able to adapt well to the environment, and respond to and apply them appropriately to the emotional energy they have, thereby acting effectively and rationally (Rendra et al., 2013). Furthermore, disclosed by Rahmasari (2012) which in his research concludes that emotional intelligence has the highest positive influence between intellectual intelligence, emotional intelligence, and spiritual intelligence toward employee performance. It can be concluded that emotional intelligence of an employee is a determining factor in performance success because in an emotional intelligence an employee can control his or her ego and desire and to understand others or colleagues to create a dynamic working group atmosphere. Wirawan (2017) points

out emotional intelligence measured based on indicators of emotional intelligence that can affect employee performance measured by indicators of a quantity of work, quality of work, timeliness of work completion, attendance in work, and cooperation in work. The result of this study shows that the increase in emotional intelligence affects the performance of employees. Improved emotional intelligence, will further improve employee performance. To enhance emotional intelligence, STPP employees are essential to continually develop things such as self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy, and social skills. Emotional intelligence creates the ability to understand oneself and others will be the skills that organizations will look for when hiring employees — the ability to associate with others, co-workers, colleagues, team members, superiors, and service users. This case will be significant for success in most jobs. Employees who have strong technical skills but are weak in emotional intelligence will find it harder to find and hold work.

Influence of Organizational Culture (X3) on Employee Performance

The result of the research shows that there is a positive influence between organizational culture on the performance of officer of STPP, Medan. Following the research was done by Anshari et al. (2014) suggests that organizational cultural values that make bureaucratic neutral, proportional and professional should be developed into an organizational culture that will help the organizations of the agencies become effective in carrying out their primary duties and functions. Although this problem is indeed a challenging task, it is critical to note that the government wants to succeed in realizing the welfare of society. In a study conducted by Hariyati (2012), indicators used to measure organizational culture are professionalism and concern. The professionalism of a lecturer is more concerned with organizational goals that have been established so that it has a good effect on the performance of the lecturer. The same is stated in Ray's research (2015) which states there is a linkage between the organizational culture and organizational performance. Officers who already understand the overall values of the organization will make those values as an organizational personality. These values and beliefs will be realized in their daily behavioral work, thus becoming individual performance. By maintaining an excellent organizational culture, organizational culture can be a social glue that helps arrest the organization together by providing a standard for what employees should say and do. Cultures help colleagues who need help and always coordinate inter-part in completing office tasks.

Influence of Training, Emotional Intelligence and Organizational Culture on the Performance

Elnaga and Imran (2013) stated that the primary purpose of each training session is to add value to employee performance, so all types of business design their training and development programs for their employees as a continuous activity. Elnaga and Imran (2013) further stated that the purpose of training is what will be achieved by employees after undergoing training programs. Some organizations plan and implement training programs for their employees without identifying goals and objectives and without knowing what the knowledge, skills, and capabilities of employees will be learned at the end of the training program and whether they will be able to achieve performance targets at work. Therefore, the company must design a training program with goals and objectives.

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human resources that have optimal performance. With training activities, employees have the opportunity to absorb new knowledge or values, so with that new knowledge, the employees can improve their profession in carrying out their assigned tasks. Wirawan (2017) points out emotional intelligence measured based on indicators of emotional intelligence that can affect employee performance measured by indicators of the quantity of work, quality of work, timeliness of work completion, attendance in work, and cooperation in work. The result of this study shows that the increase in emotional intelligence affects the performance of employees. In a study conducted by Hariyati (2012), indicators used to measure organizational culture are professionalism and concern. The professionalism of a lecturer is more concerned with organizational goals that have been established so that it has a good effect on the performance of the lecturer. The same is stated in Ray's research (2015) which states there is a linkage between the organizational culture and organizational performance. Officers who already understand the overall values of the organization will make those values as an organizational personality. These values and beliefs will be realized in their daily behavioral work, thus becoming individual performance.

Conclusion

Based on that background, this research can be done to find out whether there is significant influence between training, emotional intelligence, organizational culture as independent variables on the performance of the employee in STPP, Medan. From the result of this research, it can be concluded that among others (1) Training has a very significant effect on Performance of employees in STPP, Medan (2). Emotional Intelligence has a very significant effect on the performance of employees in STTP Medan. (3) Organizational culture has a very significant effect on the performance of employees in STTP Medan. (4). Training, emotional intelligence, and organizational culture give simultaneous and societal influences to employee performance at STPP Medan.

Suggestion

Based on the conclusions that have been suggested, the suggestions that researchers can provide are: (1) Providing training to employees according to the needs of employees. Training required by employees based on the priority level is (a). Multimedia and office (b) Outbound Management Training (OMT) (c) Guidance and counseling of students. (2) .Entering spiritual activities once a month to each employee's house on a rotation which is followed by all members of the family of the employee (3) Paste the organization culture slogan infrequently visited places and easily seen. (4) Conducting the control of the attendance of employees in the office. By the disciplined culture of the organization.

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